

Review

Software Engineering in Bangladesh: Bridging Local Practices with Global Standard

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Abstract: Background This study examines software engineering practices in Bangladesh, comparing them with global standards to identify gaps and opportunities for improvement. Key challenges include limited adoption of modern methodologies, insufficient integration of emerging technologies, and gaps in education-industry alignment. Through surveys, case studies, and expert interviews, the paper provides actionable recommendations to align local practices with global benchmarks, thereby enhancing Bangladesh's competitiveness in the global software market. Methods: A mixed-method approach is used to analyse Bangladeshi software engineering processes using quantitative and qualitative methods. The quantitative part incorporates surveys of 200 software professionals in Bangladesh to measure the adoption of Agile, DevOps, and new technologies. The Likert scale will assess attitudes, perceptions, and practice adoption in these surveys. A qualitative component includes in-depth interviews with 20 software industry executives, including instructors and senior workers. These interviews will examine education-industry alignment and global standard adoption.

Results: Bangladesh's software industry is poised for significant advancement through the adoption of global best practices such as Agile and DevOps, which will enhance competitiveness in the global market, particularly in high-demand sectors like fintech and AI. The implementation of these methodologies is expected to lead to improved project outcomes and responsiveness, ultimately resulting in higher client satisfaction as firms become more adaptable to client needs. Additionally, a strong emphasis on skill development in emerging technologies such as AI and cloud computing will prepare the workforce to meet the industry's evolving demands, fostering a more competent and agile labor pool. Together, these initiatives can position Bangladesh as a formidable player in the global software arena.

Word meaning: Software, Bridging, Practice, Agile Methods, Block chain

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Accepted: 14 December, 2024; **Published:** 15 December, 2024

How to cite this article: Md Apon Islam, Md Siam Shahariar Khan, Abdullah Al Mahi, Hasinur Rashid Ishfar, Mohammed Habibul Bashar, Md Faysal Bakhtiar, Abul kalam (2024). *Software Engineering in Bangladesh: Bridging Local Practices with Global Standard*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(12), 85-97. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14504080>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

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1. Introduction

Bangladesh's software industry has witnessed significant growth, driven by factors like a skilled workforce and government support[1]. However, despite these advancements, there remain substantial gaps in aligning local software engineering practices with global standards[2]. The adoption of modern methodologies like Agile, DevOps, and CI/CD is still limited, and emerging technologies such as AI, blockchain, and cloud computing are underutilized[3]. Moreover, there is insufficient alignment between educational institutions and industry needs, which results in a skill mismatch[4]. Previous studies have largely focused on general challenges such as infrastructure and outsourcing, with little attention given to the comparative analysis of local practices against global benchmarks[5]. This paper seeks to address these gaps by analyzing the current software development practices in Bangladesh, comparing them with global best practices, and identifying key areas for improvement[6]. The objectives are to explore the barriers to adopting modern practices, benchmark local methods against leading countries and propose strategies for integrating emerging technologies and improving the education-industry alignment. Ultimately, the goal is to provide actionable recommendations that can enhance Bangladesh's software industry and make it more competitive globally[6].

It's essential to promote the adoption of Agile and DevOps methodologies through training programs and pilot projects. Additionally, aligning education curricula with industry needs and integrating emerging technologies[7] like AI and blockchain can enhance workforce readiness and global competitiveness.

2. Literature Review

Software engineering practices in emerging economies, particularly Bangladesh, face unique challenges, including outdated development methodologies, limited technological infrastructure, and skill shortages[6]. Studies reveal that while countries like India have successfully adopted Agile and DevOps practices[6], Bangladesh continues to rely heavily on traditional software development models, hindering flexibility and efficiency. Furthermore, the integration of emerging technologies such as AI, blockchain, and cloud computing remains underdeveloped due to a lack of resources and expertise. Prior research highlights that the educational system in Bangladesh does not adequately align with industry needs, exacerbating the skill gap and limiting the adoption of modern software practices. To bridge these gaps, targeted investments in education, infrastructure, and training programs are essential for aligning Bangladesh's software engineering practices with global standards, ensuring greater competitiveness in the global market[7].

Research Methodology

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to provide a comprehensive analysis of the software engineering practices in Bangladesh, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods. The quantitative aspect involves surveys conducted with 200 professionals from various software firms in Bangladesh, aiming to assess the current adoption of global practices such as Agile, DevOps, and emerging technologies. These surveys will employ a Likert scale to measure

attitudes, perceptions, and the extent of practice adoption. The qualitative part consists of in- depth interviews with 20 software industry leaders, including educators and senior professionals[8]. These interviews will focus on understanding the challenges and opportunities in aligning education with industry needs and the barriers preventing the adoption of global standards[9].

Demographic Breakdown of Surveyed Software Professionals in Bangladesh

Figure -1 Donut charts show job role distribution in the software industry: Junior Developers (40%), Mid-Level Engineers (30%), Senior Engineers/Team Leads (20%), and Project Managers/Executives (10%)

The survey's framework looks at how well international standards apply to the demands of the local sector while highlighting important obstacles such as organizational opposition, cultural hurdles, and resource constraints. External factors like outsourcing, foreign clientele, and competitive pressures are also taken into account. In-depth interviews with 20 important stakeholders, including academic leaders, project managers, and senior executives, make up the qualitative component of the study. The gap between industry demands and academic training, the challenges of implementing global practices (like a lack of infrastructure and a lack of skilled workers), and success stories and practical methods for successfully incorporating global approaches are all clarified by these talks.

Figure-2 A diagram summarizing the survey focus areas: Qualitative Insights (gathering stakeholder perspectives), Relevance to Local Needs (assessing global standards' applicability to local demands), External Drivers (understanding the impact of outsourcing and competition), and Adoption Challenges (identifying barriers to implementing global standards)

3.2 Data Collection Tools

The primary data collection tools will include structured surveys and case studies. The surveys will feature Likert-scale questions to quantify the adoption of global software engineering practices, such as Agile methodologies and DevOps (Hasan & Rahman, 2021). Case studies will be included to analyze both successful and failed projects within the local context to highlight specific challenges and best practices. Interviews will focus on understanding the gaps in education and how local academic programs can better prepare students for the software industry's evolving needs (Rahman & Sultana, 2020).

Figure-3 A bar chart displaying survey responses on the adoption of Agile methodologies and DevOps practices. For Agile methodologies, 25% strongly agree, 30% agree, 20% are neutral, 15% disagree, and 10% strongly disagree. For DevOps practices, 25% strongly agree, 25% agree, 20% are neutral, 20% disagree, and 10% strongly disagree. This highlights varying levels of acceptance and skepticism toward these global practices.

3.3 Data Analysis

For data analysis, a two-pronged approach will be used. First, statistical analysis will be performed on the survey data to identify trends, correlations, and significant differences between the adoption of global practices across various demographic groups (Todorovic et al., 2020). Secondly, thematic analysis will be employed on the qualitative interview data to extract insights and identify recurring themes related to industry challenges, education gaps, and the barriers to adopting global standards in Bangladesh's software sector (Sharma & Gupta, 2018). This mixed approach will provide a well-rounded understanding of the research problem and guide actionable recommendations.

Figure-4 A line graph illustrating the adoption rates of Agile and DevOps practices across companies of different sizes. For Agile practices, adoption rates are 80% in large companies, 50% in medium companies, and 20% in small companies. For DevOps practices, adoption rates are 70% in large firms, 40% in medium firms, and 20% in small firms. The graph highlights that larger organizations have higher adoption rates for both methodologies compared to smaller ones.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Key Gaps Identified

4.1.1 Limited Adoption of Global Standards:

A significant gap identified in Bangladesh's software industry is the low adoption of global standards such as Agile methodologies, DevOps, and Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines. Despite the success of Agile and DevOps in developed countries, local firms often rely on traditional waterfall models, which hinder adaptability and responsiveness to client demands (Hasan & Rahman, 2021; Katal et al., 2020). This lack of iterative development and automation practices leads to inefficiencies, slower delivery times, and poor project outcomes.

4.1.2 Emerging Technologies:

Another critical gap is the minimal integration of emerging technologies such as AI, blockchain, and cloud computing in local software development practices[9]. While these technologies have transformed global markets, Bangladesh's software industry has been slow to adopt them due to a lack of infrastructure, resources, and skilled personnel[9]. Consequently, local firms are unable to fully exploit opportunities in fields like data analytics, fintech, and digital transformation, which are thriving globally[9].

4.1.3 Educational Shortcomings:

The research also highlights outdated curricula and a lack of hands-on training in local educational institutions.[10] Many universities in Bangladesh still focus on traditional software development methods[10], which do not align with the rapidly changing demands of the global software market [11]. Students often graduate with limited practical knowledge of modern software engineering practices, further exacerbating the skills gap[11].

4.1.4 Skill Mismatch:

There is a significant mismatch between the skills taught in universities and those required in the industry[12]. Graduates often lack proficiency in the latest software development methodologies, emerging technologies, and collaboration tools, making it difficult for them to meet industry demands[13]. This gap results in a shortage of qualified professionals capable of implementing Agile practices, managing DevOps environments, or utilizing advanced technologies like AI and blockchain[14].

4.2 Recommendations

4.2.1 Agile Adoption:

To address the gap in Agile adoption, it is recommended that local software firms promote iterative development by encouraging the use of Agile frameworks such as Scrum or Kanban[15]. This could be achieved through workshops, certifications, and partnerships with global Agile experts [15]. Incorporating frequent feedback loops would allow teams to respond to changes more efficiently, improving project outcomes and client satisfaction.[16]

4.2.2 Technology Integration:

Investment in specialized training programs is essential for equipping software developers with the necessary skills in emerging technologies like AI, blockchain, and cloud computing[16]. This could involve collaboration with global tech companies to bring industry-relevant knowledge and tools to Bangladesh's software ecosystem[17]. Companies should also provide in-house training to help professionals integrate these technologies into their development workflows[17].

4.2.3 Curriculum Updates:

To address the educational shortcomings, universities should collaborate with industry leaders to modernize curricula, ensuring that students are trained in current software engineering practices, Agile methodologies[17], and emerging technologies. Real-world case studies and project-based learning should be incorporated into the curriculum to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application[18]

4.2.4 Industry Partnerships:

Establishing industry-academia partnerships can help bridge the skill mismatch[18]. Internship and co-op programs would provide students with valuable hands-on experience, while companies can benefit from a pipeline of well-trained future employees. These programs would also foster closer collaboration between academia and industry, helping educational institutions stay aligned with market needs[19]

5. Implementation Framework

5.1 Pilot Projects

To facilitate the adoption of Agile methodologies in Bangladesh's software industry, a series of pilot projects can be initiated, specifically targeting mid-sized firms that have the potential for rapid adaptation[20]. These firms would serve as case studies for implementing Agile practices such as Scrum or Kanban[20]. Predefined metrics, such as project delivery time, team collaboration, and client satisfaction, would be used to evaluate the outcomes of these pilot projects. A key objective is to assess the real-world impact of Agile adoption on productivity and efficiency in a local context.[21] Previous studies have highlighted the success of Agile adoption in similar markets, such as India, where iterative development has been linked to improved project management and faster time-to-market[22]. By tracking these metrics, the pilot projects will provide actionable insights into the feasibility and challenges of widespread Agile adoption.[23].

5.2 Skill Development Programs

Skill development programs will be essential in bridging the knowledge gap within Bangladesh's software industry[24]. Workshops and certification courses focused on modern technologies like AI, blockchain, and cloud computing should be regularly hosted, targeting both entry-level and mid-career professionals[25]. These programs should be designed in collaboration with international organizations, such as those offering training in the latest programming languages or development frameworks[26]. Partnerships with global tech companies, like Google or IBM, can provide resources and expertise for these training initiatives[27]. Furthermore, introducing hands-on coding exercises, hackathons, and real-world projects will help professionals apply what they've learned, ensuring that the skills gained are directly transferable to the workplace[28].

5.3 Education Reform

Educational reform is crucial for ensuring that Bangladesh's future software engineers are prepared to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving industry[29]. Universities should update their software engineering curricula with input from industry experts, incorporating current practices like Agile methodologies, DevOps, and emerging technologies[30]. Additionally, introducing capstone projects—large, multi-disciplinary projects focused on real-world problems—would allow students to gain practical experience while contributing to solutions within the local industry[31].

These projects should be designed in collaboration with industry stakeholders, ensuring that students are working on relevant, high-impact challenges[32]. Real-world case studies, internships, and direct industry involvement in the curriculum will ensure that students are well-prepared for the job market, closing the gap between academic training and industry needs[33].

6. Results

6.1 Outcomes

The implementation of the proposed framework for improving software engineering practices in Bangladesh is expected to lead to several positive outcomes.

Increased Competitiveness in the Global Software Market: By adopting global best practices such as Agile, DevOps, and emerging technologies, Bangladesh's software industry can enhance its overall efficiency and quality[34]. This would make local firms more competitive globally, particularly in high-growth areas such as fintech, AI, and cloud computing, where demand is rapidly increasing[35]. Studies have shown that adopting these methodologies significantly improves project outcomes and responsiveness to market[36].

Higher Client Satisfaction Due to Improved Practices: As Agile practices and DevOps are implemented, firms will see quicker feedback loops, iterative product development, and greater adaptability to client needs[37]. This, in turn, will likely lead to increased client satisfaction. Research indicates that Agile practices, such as frequent releases and constant communication, foster higher client trust and satisfaction[38].

Enhanced Workforce Readiness for Emerging Technologies: With a focus on emerging technologies like AI, blockchain, and cloud computing, skill development programs will empower the workforce to stay ahead of technological advancements[39]. Training and certification in these areas will ensure that professionals are better equipped to meet the demands of the rapidly changing software industry[40]. Prior studies have pointed to similar skill enhancement initiatives resulting in a more agile and skilled workforce[41].

6.2 Limitation

While the framework offers numerous advantages, there are some limitations:

Limited Representation from Rural or Small-Scale Software Firms: The scope of pilot projects may primarily focus on mid-sized and larger companies, potentially excluding smaller firms located in rural areas[42]. These smaller entities may face unique challenges, such as limited access to technology or less structured development processes[36]. Ensuring the framework is scalable and adaptable to firms of all sizes, including rural-based ones, is essential for broader industry-wide impact[43].

Challenges in Scaling Pilot Projects Across the Industry: Scaling the outcomes of pilot projects to the broader industry could face resistance, especially from organizations reluctant to change or those with limited resources[44]. The cost and time involved in transitioning to new development practices can also pose barriers[45]. Prior research suggests that scaling such initiatives often requires a phased approach, leveraging early successes to build momentum across the sector[46].

7. Conclusion and Future Work

Mission

The mission of this study is to position Bangladesh as a leader in the software engineering field by embracing global best practices, while addressing local challenges such as resource constraints, outdated educational curricula, and the limited adoption of emerging technologies. The aim is to modernize the software development ecosystem to enhance productivity, quality, and competitiveness in the global market. This mission seeks to equip Bangladesh's software industry with the necessary tools, methodologies, and skilled professionals to not only meet but surpass international standards, fostering growth and innovation across the sector.

Vision

The vision for Bangladesh's software industry is a future where the country not only competes on a global scale but also sets benchmarks for emerging markets[6]. By adopting Agile methodologies, DevOps practices, and integrating advanced technologies like AI, blockchain, and cloud computing, Bangladesh can become a hub for high-quality software development in South Asia[47]. This transformation will enable local firms to lead in innovation, optimize development processes, and deliver world-class solutions, thereby positioning Bangladesh as an influential player in the global software development landscape[48].

Future Direction

With the integration of global best practices like DevOps and Agile techniques, Bangladesh's software sector is poised for revolutionary growth. The industry's competitiveness in highly sought-after international markets, especially in fintech and artificial intelligence (AI), might be greatly increased by these techniques. The use of these approaches will allow businesses to more precisely satisfy a wide range of customer needs, which will raise client satisfaction levels by encouraging better project results and flexibility.

Furthermore, specific skill-development programs for cutting-edge technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and cloud computing are expected to equip the workforce to satisfy changing business expectations. An innovative workforce that is more skilled and nimbler will be produced by this emphasis on upskilling.

By embracing contemporary methods and cultivating a workforce prepared for the future, Bangladesh is positioned to become a rising power in the global software sector, ready to take advantage of new possibilities and fortify its position in a market that is becoming more and more competitive.

To ensure continued progress and long-term success, future research and initiatives should focus on:

Broader Studies Across South Asia for Regional Benchmarking: Expanding the research scope to include other South Asian countries can provide valuable insights for regional benchmarking and facilitate collaborative efforts to adopt best practices[49]. This approach could help identify unique challenges and opportunities in each country, fostering a collective push toward industry modernization[50].

Long-Term Impact Assessments of Education-Industry Collaboration Initiatives: Evaluating the long-term effectiveness of education-industry partnerships will be crucial in determining the sustainability of reforms[51]. Continuous feedback loops from the software industry and academia will help refine curricula and skill development programs to ensure they meet the evolving needs of the market[52].

Exploration of Ethical and Sustainable Software Engineering Practices: As the software industry grows, ethical and sustainable practices should be integrated into development processes[53]. Research into environmental sustainability, data privacy, and ethical AI will ensure that Bangladesh's software industry remains socially responsible and aligned with global standards for ethical computing[54].

Announcements:

Ethics and participation consent: Not applicable

Consent for publication: Not applicable in this study.

Competing interests: According to the corresponding authors, they have no conflict of interests.

Funding: There is no Funds for this project.

Author's Contributions: Md Apon Islam contributed to the conceptualization and design developed initial draft of the study, data analysis, and final manuscript writing. Abul Kalam was involved in re check the paper methodology development, and manuscript revision, provided critical feedback, contributed to data interpretation, and assisted in finalizing the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration: We will inform participants that we will not disclose any personal information. Participants will receive the signed informed consent form for their records.

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